

A Comparative Study on Prediction of Heart Disease using KNN Algorithm and Naïve Bayes Algorithm

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Abstract— Heart ailment is taken into consideration as one of the key leading elements of death rate worldwide. Biomedical gadgets and numerous systems in hospitals carries large quantities of scientific records. Consequently, expertise those facts related to heart ailment is very essential to enhance prediction accuracy. The major goal of this research is to see if machine learning techniques like KNN and the Nave Bayes algorithm for classification can be used to predict vulnerability to heart disease. This article has conducted a comparative study on the performance of models created using Naïve Bayes Classifier Algorithm and K-nearest neighbor Algorithm. The datasets in our system are categorised based on a variety of medical factors. On both algorithms, this system examines those parameters. These two main Machine Learning Algorithms are used to process the datasets in the Python programming language.

Keywords:

Machine Learning Algorithms, Techniques for Data Mining, Classification Techniques, Python Programming, Artificial Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a broad field of artificial intelligence that aims to improve performance over time and uncover patterns in large amounts of data. Medical data is distinct from other types of data since it includes a wide range of traits and attributes. Furthermore, medical data might have a variety of issues, such as missing numbers, erroneous information, and sparse information. For this type of dataset, machine learning approaches are ideal. Machine learning usage is growing vastly in the medical diagnosis field, where the manual errors can be reduced with the aid of computer assisted analysis. It tremendously improves the accuracy. The diagnosis of a disease is proven to be highly reliable with machine learning techniques.

As per survey reports from around the world, each year, and nearly 20 million deaths occurred due to cardiovascular diseases (CVD). The early detection and prevention of this disease will definitely save thousands of lives, and mortality rate can be enormously reduced with the co-operation of patients in taking their treatments on time. Cardiovascular

diseases includes a broad spectrum of ailments affecting human heart. Lifestyle changes such as lack of physical activity, intake of foods high in saturated fats, sodium and added sugars are becoming very common even in all the age groups significantly lowering their overall health especially heart. Similarly bad habits and addictions like smoking, high intake of alcoholic drinks, high cholesterol food, junk food, and sedentary lifestyles are all considered as the key leading causes of heart disease.

This study aims to provide a comparative analysis on various aspects of Naïve Bayes and KNN algorithm in predicting heart disease based on a same dataset available in the public domain. Machine learning classification algorithms such as Nave Bayes and KNN Classification models are used to apply classification techniques to the dataset. These models are used to improve the precision of categorization techniques. On a given dataset, this model does both classification and prediction. The python programming language is used to create these models. The Naive Bayes algorithm and the KNN algorithm are two of the most basic types of algorithms that are also the easiest to build. The Nave Bayes Classifier is based on the Bayes Theorem and the concept of probability. It often plays a vital part in the decision-making process. The principle of feature similarity is used by the K-nearest neighbor classifier. It can be used to tackle problems involving classification and regression.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section examines and evaluates some papers that are connected to similar investigations - Machine Learning Algorithms for Heart Disease Prediction. Maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications in [1]. Based on the Naive Bayes Classifier, the authors created a method to predict the possibility or likelihood of developing heart disease. Their system achieved an accuracy level of 87%.

In their article "Computational iintelligence data mining strategy for diagnosis of heart disease,"[2] M.A. Jabbar et al. offered another method. The authors of this study tried to significantly improve the accuracy of heart disease predictions. They used a variety of strategies, including discretization pre-processing techniques and a genetic

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algorithm applied to a Nave Bayes classifier, to produce encouraging results.

Agung W. Setiawan, Dadi Rahmat, Andika A. Putra, Hamrin in their research paper titled "Heart Disease Prediction Using K-Nearest Neighbor"[3] proposed several methods like KNN imputation, standardization, and feature selection with SelectKBest method. The performance is validated by 10-Fold Cross Validation. Their system provided a better precision of 95.50%, recall of 84.16%, and accuracy 89.28% for 0.59 ms.

M.A. Jabbar et.al proposed "Heart disease prediction using nearest neighbor and GA" [4]. In their work Genetic Algorithm (GA) which is a heuristic search algorithm efficient in solving searching and optimizing problems is used as a feature selection measure. When creating a classifier, higher-ranking characteristics are chosen. Their system outperformed other alternatives in terms of accuracy.

Unlike previous research on heart illness classifications, this paper proposes a comparative strategy for effective heart disease diagnosis classification utilising machine learning techniques such as Nave Bayes and K closest neighbour models.

III. HEART DISEASE

A heart is considered as one of the crucial vital organ like brain in a human body. Heart is the main organ of our cardiovascular system and the primary organ of our circulatory system. If a heart fails to perform its functions properly due to any reasons, it will gradually affect other vital organs of the human body like lungs, kidney, brain, by depriving blood and other nourishments along with oxygen. According to many World Health Organization (WHO) statistics, one-third of the world's population perished from heart-related disorders in the last two to three years. Heart disease will be the most common cause of death in both emerging and developed countries by the year 2025.

The heart circulates blood through the circulatory system's blood vessels, supplying oxygen and nutrients to our cells. Blood carries oxygen and other nutrients throughout the body and aids in the elimination of metabolic wastes. If blood circulation in the body is disrupted, numerous organs, including the cerebrum in our brain, suffer from oxygen deprivation, and if the heart entirely fails, death occurs within minutes.

Heart disease risk factor include:

- High Cholesterol
- High blood pressure
- Diabetics
- Smoking
- Stress
- High alcohol intake
- Overweight or obese
- Family history of coronary illness

Symptoms of Heart attack:

- Shortness of breath while physical activities
- Tightness, chest pain or discomfort in the chest
- Pain that spread to left or right arm or to neck, jaw, back or stomach
- Fatigue
- Cold sweat and unsteadiness
- Rapid or irregular heart beat
- Heart burn or abnormal pain

Types of cardiovascular disease:

- Cardiac arrest
- Heart valve disease
- Pericardial disease
- Cardiomyopathy
- Congenital heart disease.
- Stroke, among other things

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Source

The dataset used in our system for predicting heart disease is borrowed from UCI Machine learning repository. UCI is a collection of databases, also includes domain theories and data generators that are used for implementing various empirical analysis of machine learning algorithms. All of the datasets utilised in this study are real clinical datasets. The dataset contains 300 data examples with 14 clinical factors that were chosen at random. The clinical parameters of the dataset include calcium-score, level of blood pressure, type of chest pain, electrocardiographic result, and other tests used to diagnose heart related problems.

B. Naive Bayes Classifier

A Naive Bayes classifier is a statistically based classifier, specifically a family of basic "probabilistic classifiers" whose foundations are based on Bayes Theorem. It has strong independent assumptions among the features. Probabilities are used to build this classifier. According to Bayes theorem, given two events A and B, P (A) is the prior probability and P (A|B) is the posterior probability, it can be written as follows.

$P(A|B) = P(B|A) P(A)/P(B)$ and $P(B|A)$ is computed as $P(A \cap B) = P(A)$

These Bayesian probabilities are the core principles used to determine the most likely event to occur for a certain instance given all of the training data. The training data is used to construct conditional probabilities. The conditional independence model of each predictor given the target class is the foundation of the Naive Bayes model [5]. The

most accurate prediction is provided by this classifier (given the necessary assumptions). It can also handle numeric and discrete attribute values. The algorithm for this method is provided in Algorithm 1 below.

a) *Algorithm 1:* This algorithm uses a Bayes classifier to provide a step by step procedure for predicting cardiac disease.

As input, there is a data set on heart illness.

Output: Classify the patient dataset as having or not having heart disease.

Step 1: Read the inputted dataset in the system.

Step 2: Apply particle swarm optimization to the dataset for feature selection.

Step 3: Remove any features with a low Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) value.

Step 4: Apply the Naive Bayes classifier on the relevant features that have been found.

Step 5: Finally, assess the model's effectiveness.

For clarity, the above algorithm can be divided into two sections, section 1 (step2 & step 3) performs processing of dataset and feature subset selection. In section 2 (step 4 & step 5) The Naive Bayes classifier is applied to the obtained relevant features and the performance is evaluated in terms of accuracy.

Accuracy = (number of successfully categorised objects/ total number of objects in test set)

The dataset is separated into training and testing data using the cross validation technique.

b) *Experimental Results:* Naive Bayes classification of Data Mining has significantly proven to be an effective approach for the prediction of Cardiovascular disease. Naive Bayes has an accuracy or prediction rate of 98.8636 percent. Here, a number of parameters are used to predict the presence or absence of cardiac disease like sex, age, chest pain type, serum cholesterol level, blood pressure at rest, blood sugar levels after a fast, electrocardiographic results during rest, maximal heart rate attained, angina induced by exercise and old peak etc.

C. K-nearest neighbor classifier (KNN)

K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) is a nonparametric, slow, and basic classifier. When all of the characteristics are continuous, KNN is preferred. KNN, also known as case-based reasoning, has been employed in a wide range of applications, including pattern recognition and statistical estimation. In order to figure out what class an unknown sample belongs to, the nearest neighbour must be identified. Because of its rapid convergence speed and simplicity, KNN is favoured over other categorization methods. The KNN classification is divided into two steps.

- 1) Determine the number of examples, k, in the dataset that are closest to the instance, say X, in the first stage.

- 2) These k instances vote in the second step to select the class of instance, say X.

KNN accuracy is determined by the distance measure and K value. Euclidian distance and cosine are two methods for calculating the distance between two points. KNN computes its K nearest neighbours to evaluate the new unknown sample and assigns a class by majority voting. The medical data collection includes a significant number of features that are frequently redundant and irrelevant. If the data set contains these kind of features, the classifier's performance may suffer. The accuracy of the classifier is enhanced and the running time is reduced by excluding redundant features. Algorithm for this method is shown below as Algorithm 2.

a) *Algorithm 2:* Prediction of heart disease by using KNN.

Input: Dataset on heart illness.

Output: Classify the patient dataset as having or not having heart disease.

Step 1: Input the information into the system.

Step 2: Use pre-processing procedures to fill in the missing values.

Step 3: Select the features based on the outcomes of using PSO as an FSS.

Step 4: Remove any features that are no longer needed (features with low values of PSO).

Step 5: Use (KNN+IQR) on the most predominant features.

Step 6: Evaluate the KNN model's performance.

b) *Experimental Results:* Their model has an accuracy of 75.18 for k=5 and 86.14 for k=7. The KNN+PSO model's findings indicate that their proposed model will improve accuracy at a greater level.

V. CONCLUSION

The accuracy achieved with the KNN technique was 86.14 percent, while the accuracy achieved with the Naive Bayes classifier was 98.86 percent. Because it is a linear classifier, Naive Bayes is faster than K-NN when dealing with large amounts of data. Due to the calculations necessary for each new step in the process, k-nn is noted to be slower when dealing with big amounts of data. Naive Bayes is usually quite accurate when dealing with big volumes of data. In the case of K-NN, the error rate lowers as the value of k in K-NN increases until it achieves the optimal Bayes factor (for k tends to infinity).

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